

ЕКОНОМІЧНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ГАЛУЗЕЙ ТА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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БЕБКО С. В.
ВЕРБОВЕЦЬКИЙ М. І.

Strategic approaches to the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the conditions of post-war recovery

The subject of the research is the theoretical aspects of strategic approaches to the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the conditions of post-war recovery.

The aim of the research is to determine the main strategies for the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the conditions of post-war recovery.

Research methods. In writing the article, various research methods were used: literature analysis; situational analysis; SWOT analysis; marketing research; PESTLE analysis; competitive analysis; risk analysis; factor analysis; tabular and graphical method, etc.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that the war started in Ukraine by the Russian Federation in 2022 has put significant pressure on economic stability, creating unpredictability, market fluctuations, changing consumer priorities and restricting access to resources, which, in turn, requires enterprises to quickly adapt their strategies, including product policy, in order not only to survive but also to remain competitive. It is determined that the conditions of post-war recovery will be complex and will require a systematic approach to the formation and development of the commodity policy of enterprises, which is a key element of their strategic success in the face of economic turbulence and instability. It is proved that the strategy of commodity policy will be the tool that will allow enterprises to restore their sustainability, ensure market presence and meet the needs of consumers. The conditions of post-war recovery for the effective functioning of enterprises are determined, which include certain obstacles, such as disruption of supply chains, changes in consumer behavior, fluctuations in demand, reduction of production capacity and economic instability. The author proposes the main strategic approaches to the formation and development of the commodity policy of enterprises in the context of post-war recovery, namely: changes in consumer behavior in the context of post-war recovery; reorientation of production capacities; pricing in conditions of economic instability; management of the product range and life cycle in conditions of turbulence; logistics solutions and ensuring continuity of supply; innovations and digitalization of marketing activities of enterprises. The external and internal factors influencing the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the context of post-war recovery are determined.

Scope of the results. Marketing product policy, strategic development, enterprise management, enterprise competitiveness, enterprise economics, military conflicts.

Conclusions. It is proved that the commodity policy of the enterprise determines the strategic direction of its activities in the market, focusing on the choice of assortment, pricing, distribution and sale of products. In the context of post-war recovery, this is of particular importance, since enterprises are forced to adapt to new economic realities, change approaches to strategic management and adapt their products to market needs. It is established that an important aspect is the use of digital technologies to maintain competitive advantages and ensure stable operation in the post-war recovery. It is determined that those enterprises that can quickly adapt their product policy and implement innovative solutions will have a better chance not only to survive but also to strengthen their market position after the end of the military conflict.

Keywords: strategy, product policy, enterprise management, post-war recovery, pricing, consumers, competitiveness.

БЕБКО С. В.
ВЕРБОВЕЦЬКИЙ М. І.

Стратегічні підходи до формування та розвитку товарної політики підприємства в умовах післявоєнного відновлення

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні аспекти стратегічних підходів до формування та розвитку товарної політики підприємства в умовах післявоєнного відновлення.

Метою дослідження є визначення основних стратегій щодо формування та розвитку товарної політики підприємства в умовах післявоєнного відновлення.

Методи дослідження. При написанні статті було використано різні методи дослідження: аналіз літератури; ситуаційний аналіз; метод SWOT-аналізу; маркетингові дослідження; PESTLE-аналіз; конкурентний аналіз; аналіз ризиків; факторний аналіз; таблично-графічний метод та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що війна розпочата в Україні з боку РФ у 2022р. створила значний тиск на економічну стабільність, створивши непередбачуваність, коливання ринків, зміну споживчих пріоритетів та обмеження доступу до ресурсів, що, у свою чергу, для підприємств вимагає оперативного адаптування своїх стратегій, включаючи товарну політику, аби не лише вижити, але й зберегти конкурентоспроможність. Визначено, що умови післявоєнного відновлення будуть складними та вимагатимуть системного підходу до формування та розвитку товарної політики підприємств, яка є ключовим елементом їх стратегічного успіху в умовах економічних турбуленцій та нестабільності. Доведено, що стратегія товарної політики стане тим інструментом, який дозволить підприємствам відновити свою стійкість, забезпечити присутність на ринку та відповідати потребам споживачів. Визначено, умови післявоєнного відновлення для ефективного функціонування підприємств, що передбачають певні перешкоди, такі як порушення ланцюгів постачання, зміни в поведінці споживачів, коливання попиту, зниження рівня виробничих потужностей та нестабільність економіки. Запропоновано основні стратегічні підходи до формування та розвитку товарної політики підприємств в умовах післявоєнного відновлення, а саме: зміни в поведінці споживачів в умовах післявоєнного відновлення; переорієнтація виробничих потужностей; ціноутворення в умовах економічної нестабільності; управління асортиментом та життєвим циклом товару в умовах турбулентності; логістичні рішення та забезпечення безперервності постачання; інновації та цифровізація маркетингової діяльності підприємств. Визначено зовнішні та внутрішні чинники впливу на формування та розвиток товарної політики підприємства в умовах післявоєнного відновлення.

Галузь застосування результатів. Маркетингова товарна політика, стратегічний розвиток, управління підприємствами, конкурентоспроможність підприємств, економіка підприємства, воєнні конфлікти.

Висновки. Доведено, що товарна політика підприємства визначає стратегічний напрямок його діяльності на ринку, спрямовуючи увагу на вибір асортименту, ціноутворення, дистрибуцію та продаж продукції. В умовах післявоєнного відновлення це набуває особливої уваги, оскільки підприємства

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змушені адаптуватися до нових економічних реалій, змінювати підходи до стратегічного управління та пристосовувати свою продукцію до потреб ринку. Встановлено, що важливим аспектом є використання цифрових технологій для збереження конкурентних переваг та забезпечення стабільної роботи в умовах післявоєнного відновлення. Визначено, що ті підприємства, які зможуть швидко адаптувати свою товарну політику та впровадити інноваційні рішення, матимуть більше шансів не тільки вижити, але й зміцнити свої позиції на ринку після завершення воєнного конфлікту.

Ключові слова: стратегія, товарна політика, управління підприємствами, післявоєнне відновлення, ціноутворення, споживачі, конкурентоспроможність.

Formulation of the problem. The war started in Ukraine by the Russian Federation in 2022 has already put significant pressure on economic stability, creating unpredictability, market fluctuations, changing consumer priorities and limited access to resources, which, in turn, requires businesses to quickly adapt their strategies, including product policy, in order not only to survive but also to remain competitive. The post-war recovery environment will be challenging and will require a systematic approach to the development of enterprises in all sectors of the economy. A particularly important aspect will be the formation and development of the companies' commodity policy, which is a key element of their strategic success in the face of economic turbulence and instability. The commodity policy strategy will be the tool that will allow companies to restore their sustainability, ensure their market presence and meet the needs of consumers. Consumer demand and behavior may change, which will require prompt response and adaptation by businesses to changes in the external and internal environment. The ability of businesses to formulate and develop a product policy in the post-war recovery will allow them to minimize risks and find new opportunities for growth and competitiveness in general. Also, in the post-war situation, enterprises will face conditions of limited access to material and human resources, which will force them to revise the processes of production and management of the product range. Therefore, the relevance of the topic lies in the ability of businesses to analyze strategic approaches to the formation and development of a commodity policy that takes into account social needs, helps stabilize the situation in the country and contributes to economic recovery in the post-war period. Businesses can support humanitarian initiatives and adapt their commodity policy to the needs of the affected regions, which will increase their reputation and public trust.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The issue of strategies for the formation

and development of the commodity policy of enterprises in the context of post-war recovery is quite specific and relevant in modern conditions, especially given the obstacles arising from military conflicts. Although direct research with an emphasis on martial law is still relatively new, there are a number of scholars who have studied the commodity policy of enterprises in the context of crises and unforeseen circumstances. Among the main authors whose works may be useful in the context of this topic are: I. Ansoff is the author of the concept of strategic management, which can be applied under martial law to adapt commodity policy. His works deal with management issues in times of instability and changes in the external environment; M. Porter – known for his research on competitive strategy and business adaptation to difficult economic conditions, in particular in times of crisis; K. Philip – his works on marketing, product policy and branding strategies contain useful tools for adapting product strategy in times of unforeseen circumstances; A. Slivotsky – researched issues of risk management and crisis in business, which can be adapted to the context of the Among the Ukrainian scholars who have studied the issues of commodity policy and enterprise management in the context of the crisis and post-war recovery, it should be noted: V. Savchuk, who studied crisis management and its impact on enterprise strategies; O. Honcharenko, who studied management strategies in emergency situations and crises. However, the issue of strategic approaches to the formation and development of the commodity policy of enterprises in the context of post-war recovery requires further in-depth consideration.

Presenting main material. The post-war recovery environment for business operations involves certain obstacles, where companies will face a number of challenges, such as supply chain disruptions, changes in consumer behavior, fluctuations in demand, reduced production capacity, and economic instability. In these circumstances, it will be especially important to review the strategies of the compa-

nies' commodity policy in order to adapt them to the new realities and ensure competitiveness. A company's product policy is a set of decisions related to the development, production, promotion and sale of products, including the definition of the product range, pricing policy, development of new products and measures to promote the product on the market. In the context of post-war recovery, it is necessary to review strategic approaches to the formation and development of product policy, taking into account the post-war imbalance and instability of the external environment [1; 3; 6; 8; 12; 15; 16].

The main strategic approaches to the formation and development of the commodity policy of enterprises in the post-war recovery include the following: changes in consumer behavior in the post-war recovery; reorientation of production capacities; pricing in conditions of economic instability; management of the product range and life cycle in conditions of turbulence; logistics solutions and ensuring continuity of supply; innovations and digitalization of marketing activities of enterprises. Now let's take a closer look at these approaches [2; 7; 11; 18; 22].

1. Changes in consumer behavior in the post-war recovery. The primary factor that will influence the company's product policy during the post-war recovery period will be the change in consumer sentiment. In times of war, people begin to save resources and change their consumer priorities. After the war is over, demand will increase not only for basic necessities, but also for luxury goods and non-first use products that are currently falling out of the focus of consumer interest. This will mean that companies will need to adapt their product range to meet the changes in demand [9; 13; 21]. The main tasks here will be:

- transition to the production of goods that will be in stable demand in the post-war environment;
- expanding the range of goods of both primary and secondary necessity;
- adaptation of goods to new consumer needs.

2. Reorientation of production facilities. One of the important aspects of commodity policy is the organization of production. Under martial law, production faces many challenges, such as shortages of raw materials, supply disruptions, and damage to production facilities and infrastructure. In the post-war period, companies should consider the following strategies to effectively manage their production processes [4; 10; 19]:

- diversification of suppliers – searching for alternative suppliers and creating stocks of raw materials, which will reduce the risks associated with supply disruptions;

- flexibility of production processes – companies should be ready to quickly reorient their production lines to manufacture products that are in demand both in war and post-war conditions;

- localization of production – in order to avoid logistical problems, companies can relocate part of their production facilities closer to consumers.

3. Pricing in the context of economic instability in the postwar recovery. After the end of the war, the country's economy will face changes in prices, which are subject to frequent fluctuations due to inflation, fluctuations in the national currency, and changes in supply and demand. Therefore, the commodity policy should take into account the peculiarities of pricing in the period of post-war economic instability, where it is necessary to pay attention to the following factors [5; 14; 17]:

- dynamic pricing – enterprises should respond promptly to changes in the economic situation by adjusting prices depending on market conditions;

- flexibility in price offers – it is important to offer different product options for consumers with different income levels, providing access to budget products or offering a premium segment to maintain customer loyalty;

- adaptation of pricing to changing costs – businesses should review prices to reflect changes in production and logistics costs, while maintaining a balance between profitability and competitiveness.

4. Assortment and product life cycle management in a turbulent environment. Assortment management in the post-war recovery requires flexibility and the ability to make rapid changes. Products that were popular in wartime may lose their relevance, while products that were not previously in high demand may become a priority [16; 19; 23]. Here you need to pay attention to:

- analysis of the market and consumer sentiment – regular research of changes in the market will help identify new consumer needs and promptly adjust the assortment;

- reduction or expansion of the assortment – companies should be able to quickly withdraw unpopular products from the market and introduce new items that meet current demand;

- product life cycle management – for products that have reached the stage of maturity or decline, businesses should look for ways to extend their life cycle or remove them from the market completely.

5. Logistics solutions and ensuring continuity of supply. War often disrupts well-established supply chains. In the context of post-war recovery, it is important for companies to find new approaches to ensure uninterrupted supply of raw materials and finished products, namely [20; 22; 23]:

- search for alternative and more efficient delivery routes – as traditional routes may be blocked, destroyed, or mined, businesses should look for new logistics solutions using alternative vehicles or routes;
- optimization of stocks – increasing the amount of storage of products in warehouses, which can help to avoid supply disruptions;
- cooperation with government agencies – companies can receive support in the form of subsidies or preferences from the state to overcome logistical obstacles.

6. Innovations and digitalization of marketing activities of enterprises. The recovery period will force companies to look for new technological solutions to ensure further effective work, where business digitalization will automate processes, reduce costs and increase flexibility in decision-making [11; 14; 19; 21; 23]. The main elements of this strategic approach will be:

- increase in online sales – businesses should more actively implement digital sales channels, which will reduce dependence on physical stores;

- automation of production processes – the use of the latest technologies to automate production and logistics will reduce dependence on human resources, which have become limited in the war;

- development of digital marketing tools – the use of social networks, contextual advertising and other online promotion tools will allow to maintain interaction with consumers even in conditions of limited physical presence.

Thus, summarizing the above, it can be stated that the main strategic approaches to the formation of product policy are: analysis of market conditions; formation of assortment policy; pricing and pricing policy; distribution and sales strategies (Fig. 1) [11; 15; 16; 19; 21].

The formation and development of an enterprise's commodity policy in the context of post-war recovery also depends on many external and internal factors (Table 1). The war and its consequences significantly change the economic, social and political situation in the country, so companies have to take all aspects into account [18; 19; 22; 23].

Table 1. Influence of factors on the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the conditions of post-war recovery

Fig. 1. The main strategic approaches to the formation and development of the commodity policy of enterprises in the post-war recovery

Table 1. Influence of factors on the formation and development of the enterprise's commodity policy in the conditions of post-war recovery

EXTERNAL FACTORS		INTERNAL FACTORS
The economic environment	<p>Inflation rate The post-war economy may suffer from high inflation, which affects the purchasing power of the population and the pricing policy of businesses.</p> <p>Recovery of the financial system The availability of credit and investment may be limited, affecting the company's ability to invest in new products or production facilities.</p> <p>Reduced production capacity Destruction of infrastructure may reduce the ability to produce and supply goods</p>	<p>Financial resources Post-war recovery may be accompanied by limited financial resources. Businesses should adapt their product policy to the available budgets for new product development, raw material procurement, and modernization of production facilities</p>
Political environment	<p>Government policies and support The government may introduce economic recovery programs that include financial subsidies, soft loans or preferences for businesses that participate in the reconstruction.</p> <p>Regulatory changes Post-war governments may introduce new laws on taxation, customs barriers or regulations that affect a company's product policy</p> <p>Rehabilitation of international trade Restoration of ties with international partners or the introduction of new sanctions may affect the ability to export or import</p>	<p>Production facilities The condition of production assets, such as equipment, technology and infrastructure, is an important factor where modernization or restoration of production facilities can affect production volumes and product quality</p>
Social environment	<p>Changes in demand Consumer needs and priorities may change after the war</p> <p>Migration processes Loss of population due to migration or destruction of infrastructure may lead to changes in the geographical distribution of consumers</p> <p>Changes in consumer behavior Due to the trauma of war and general economic instability, consumers may be more cautious in spending, which requires adaptation of marketing policies</p>	<p>Human resources potential The qualifications, experience and number of employees, their ability to work in new conditions and adapt to changes have a significant impact on the development and implementation of commodity policy</p>
Technological changes	<p>Innovations During the recovery, new technologies may be introduced to improve production efficiency and increase competitiveness</p> <p>Restoration of infrastructure Gradual restoration of production and logistics capacities will affect the company's ability to expand its product range and improve the quality of goods</p>	<p>Assortment policy Businesses should assess the relevance of their assortment and its compliance with new market conditions. It is important to introduce innovations quickly, change consumer needs and adapt the assortment to these changes</p>
Competitive environment	<p>Emergence of new players in the market After the war, new businesses or foreign companies may emerge to compete for markets</p> <p>Changes in market structure The destruction or weakening of some businesses may change the market structure, creating new niches for development</p>	<p>Marketing strategy The effectiveness of promotion channels, the availability of communication tools, and opportunities for product positioning are important aspects of product policy, where businesses should be prepared to change their approaches to advertising, pricing, and customer service</p>
Environmental factors	<p>Restoration of ecosystems War can lead to environmental disasters, which requires the introduction of new production standards, including environmentally friendly technologies</p> <p>State environmental regulations Restoration of post-war ecology may be a priority for the government, which will lead to new requirements for environmental responsibility</p>	<p>Inventory and logistics Inventory management and the ability to deliver goods in a timely manner depends on internal logistics processes, including their effectiveness after the disruptions caused by the war</p>
Research and innovation policy	<p>Research and innovation potential A company's ability to innovate and research market trends is an important component for developing new products or modernizing existing ones</p>	<p>Organizational structure The internal management system and the ability of managers to make flexible decisions on product policy and adaptation of the enterprise to new conditions also play a crucial role in post-war recovery</p>

Therefore, the formation and development of an enterprise's commodity policy in the context of post-war recovery depends on many external and internal factors that affect the ability of an enterprise to adapt to new realities and ensure the competitiveness of its products.

Conclusions

The commodity policy of an enterprise determines the strategic direction of its activities in the market, focusing on the choice of assortment, pricing, distribution and sale of products. In the context of post-war recovery, this becomes even more important, as enterprises are forced to adapt to new economic realities, change approaches to strategic management and adapt their products to market needs. An important aspect is the use of digital technologies to maintain competitive advantages and ensure stable operations even in crisis conditions. Companies that can quickly adapt their product policy and implement innovative solutions will have a better chance of not only surviving but also strengthening their market position after the end of the military conflict.

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Data about the authors

Svitlana Bebko,

Professor of the Department of Marketing and Communication Design, Kyiv National University of

Technologies and Design, Doctor of Science in Economics, Associate Professor

e-mail: bebko.sv@knutd.edu.ua

Mykhailo Verbovetskyi,

Master student of the Department of Marketing and Communication Design, Kyiv National University of Technologies and Design

e-mail: mverbovetskiy@gmail.com

Дані про авторів

Бєбко Світлана Вікторівна,

професор кафедри маркетингу та комунікаційного дизайну, Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну, д.е.н., доцент

e-mail: bebko.sv@knutd.edu.ua

Вербовецький Михайло Іванович,

Магістр кафедри маркетингу та комунікаційного дизайну, Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну

e-mail: mverbovetskiy@gmail.com

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КРАМЧЕНКО Р. А.

Підходи до формування виробничої програми підприємства

Предметом дослідження є виробнича програма підприємства.

Метою дослідження є визначення підходів до формування виробничої програми підприємства.

Методи дослідження. У статті використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, метод аналізу і синтезу, порівняльний метод, метод узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті визначено підходи до формування виробничої програми підприємства. Наведені основні елементи виробничої програми. Охарактеризовані переваги ефективної виробничої програми підприємства. Відзначено роль контролю та моніторингу, які гарантують своєчасність виконання виробничих планів.

Висновки. Одним із важливих елементів ефективної виробничої програми є інтеграція новітніх технологій, які сприяють автоматизації та оптимізації виробничих процесів. Використання сучасних програмних рішень для управління виробництвом дає можливість зменшити витрати, підвищити швидкість обробки замовлень та покращити керованість процесів. Інвестиції в обладнання та технології зможуть сприяти підвищенню конкурентоспроможності підприємства на ринку. Для забезпечення стійкості виробництва підприємствам необхідно також зосереджуватись на екологічних аспектах своєї діяльності. Впровадження принципів сталого розвитку та енергоефективності зможе покращити імідж компанії, що, в свою чергу, привертає нових клієнтів. Участь у соціально відповідальних ініціативах також сприяє формуванню позитивної репутації підприємства. Важливою складовою виробничої програми є навчання персоналу. Якісне навчання працівників забезпечує успішність виконання виробничих планів. Розвиток корпоративної культури, що впроваджує інновації, є додатковим чинником, який дасть можливість підприємству досягати нових успіхів в умовах динамічного ринку. Крім впровадження новітніх технологій, підприємства повинні активно досліджувати та адаптуватися до змін у споживачькій поведінці та ринкових трендах. Це є використання аналітики великих даних для прогнозування попиту, що надає можливість своєчасно коригувати виробничі плани та зменшувати витрати. Здатність реагувати на зміни в ринку є вирішальним фактором для підвищення конкурентоспроможності.